

DIDACTIC CONDITIONS OF FORMING CREATIVE THINKING SKILLS IN STUDENT

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ANNOTATION. In this article, social didactic directions, conditions of the formation of creative thinking skills in students, and aspects of creative thinking related to social experience are discussed. In this process, the teacher's tasks are discussed, and the article can be widely used by the scientific and pedagogical community, students, and researchers.

Key words: creative thinking, creative technologies, creativity, creative ability, creative skills, activity methods, didactic approaches, and didactic conditions.

Students' creative thinking process develops in direct connection with social reality. This reality is expressed as a social experience of the people in the pedagogical process that teaches students to think creatively and requires interrelated pedagogical conditions. These conditions appear as a mechanism for developing students' creative thinking skills.

Students think creatively and perform creative activities based on their feelings and experiences. As an opportunity for creative activity, students can express their views in a creative way, reflect their feelings, experiences, and personal views in the products of creative activity, and create examples of creativity. Such examples of creative thinking are important for the formation of creative qualities in students. Students' creative thinking skills are demonstrated through interaction, dialogue, and

creative activity. For the manifestation of creative skills, students should creatively assimilate a lot of information and demonstrate their cognitive abilities during the educational process. Students' introduction to interpersonal communication and dialogue with the help of educational materials and additional information will help them understand that examples of creativity are valuable to them.

Educational materials in the moral-aesthetic direction occupy a leading place in the acquisition of creative thinking skills in students. Creative thinking helps students develop analytical skills. As a result, students will have the experience of cognitive activities such as engaging in mutual dialogue, conducting research, describing their experiences, and creating creative products. The effectiveness of the educational process increases as a result of the organization of educational situations aimed at forming students' creative thinking skills. In these pedagogical situations, the formation of cognitive competencies in students is important.

The experience of analytical activity formed by students helps them understand the meaning of their actions. Emphasis is placed on the systematic formation of creative thinking skills in educational materials presented to students in certain pedagogical processes. Creative thinking skills can only be formed as a result of students' thorough mastering and cognitive understanding of these educational materials. As a result of organizing learning situations that serve to systematically form creative thinking skills, students have the opportunity to express their experiences and feelings.

Students' creative thinking skills are developed through activities such as selection, evaluation, decision-making, and the expression of personal feelings. For this, it is required to incorporate didactic tools and knowledge that serve to develop students' creative thinking skills into the content of educational materials. For this purpose, it is important for the teacher to design the processes of cognitive acquisition of knowledge and social experience by students.

Cognitive technologies, cultural values, and artistic-aesthetic knowledge can be included among the tools that develop students' creative thinking skills. Information, values, and knowledge of artistic and aesthetic content that encourage students to show cognitive activity should form the main part of the educational content, that is, the macro content. Educational content and the cultural and social experience of the Uzbek people play an important role in the development of students' creative thinking skills.

The activity of science teachers in developing students' creative thinking skills is important. In this case, it is important for the teacher to organize the process of developing students' creative thinking skills based on a cognitive approach, to regularly analyze pedagogical situations related to the manifestation of creativity in students, and to identify and regularly fill the gaps in this direction, to give priority to imitating real reality in order to create situations that encourage creative thinking in the educational process. is important. It is necessary for students to realize that as a result of cognitive acquisition of knowledge, they have the opportunity to perform creative activities. They should realize that the knowledge they have learned is important for their future development. It is necessary for students to be satisfied with the results of their creative activities as a result of mastering educational materials, and for the development of their creative thinking skills.

Students are required to strive for cognitive mastery of educational materials, and teachers are required to regularly support their creative thinking activities. The formation of a special interest in creative processes among students is the basis for the development of creative thinking skills in them. As a result of creative thinking, students acquire the experience of creativity and initiative. In this process, teachers should acquire the experience of organizing students' creative thinking processes based on an innovative approach.

First of all, teachers need to be able to effectively use cognitive technologies and developmental education methods. As a result of the use of these technologies,

a creative educational environment is created. The activity of creative thinking carried out in such an educational process forms the experience of teachers in the use of methods of cognitive acquisition of educational materials.

Science teachers and class leaders should have a program to develop creative thinking skills in students. It is important for students to be able to demonstrate creative ways of thinking, to collaborate creatively with classmates and teachers in this direction. Science teachers are required to encourage students to regularly think creatively, to create reflective experience in them. As a result of creative thinking, students develop a positive behavioral experience, a sense of sophistication, a sense of beauty and a desire for creativity.

Students strive to create unique things as a result of creative thinking. This helps them to develop mental peace and work skills. One of the main possibilities of cognitive technologies is to create a favorable situation for students to perform analytical activities, creative thinking, self-expression as a subject of the creative process, regular self-development. Students with creative thinking skills can always express themselves as subjects of the creative process. Students have the opportunity to use different forms of reflection in the creative learning process. With the help of such an analytical activity, students will justify the event, choose the necessary methods, and check the results.

The reflection formed in the students can serve to acquire new knowledge and information, apply it, show the results of creative activity, and implement critical thinking processes.

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